

BEYOND RELIGION: DECODING THE SOCIO-POLITICAL FOUNDATIONS OF EXTREMISM IN CONTEMPORARY PAKISTAN

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<https://currentsignjournal.com/index.php/JCS/index>

Beyond Religion: Decoding the Socio-Political Foundations of Extremism in Contemporary Pakistan

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Abstract

Pakistan's identity as an Islamic state has engendered persistent challenges, positioning it in tension with its foundational vision as a laboratory for Islamic principles. Over seven decades, this religious nationalism has fuelled extremism, undermining its ideological aspirations. This paper investigates the socio-economic, political, and geo-strategic factors driving this phenomenon, offering a

comprehensive historical analysis. It argues that Pakistan's internal struggles reflect a self-inflicted crisis rooted in its inception. Focusing on Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Punjab, the study examines the contemporary surge of extremism, interrogating whether it is an intractable legacy of the nation's history, positing that extremism is not merely a reaction to external pressures but a structural outcome of domestic policies and identity politics. This analysis contributes to understanding Pakistan as a state ensnared by its own ideological and strategic choices, questioning the depth of extremism's historical embeddedness within its socio-political fabric.

Keywords: Pakistan; Extremism, Religious Extremism, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Punjab, Counter Extremism,

Introduction

What is objectionable, what is dangerous about extremists is not that they are extreme, but that they are intolerant. The evil is not what they say about their cause, but what they say about their opponents.

Frustrated by rejection, he condemns the motives, the morals or the patriotism of all who disagree. Whether he is inflamed by politics or religion or drinking water, he still spreads selfish slogans and false fears.

Robert F. Kennedy¹

For long, Pakistan has faced severe threats of extremism, sectarianism, terrorism, and militancy, adversely affecting its economic stability and social harmony, increasing a sense of insecurity among the people. The assassination of Salman Taseer, the attempted murder of Malala Yousafzai,

¹ Robert Francis Kennedy, "Extremism, Left and Right," in *The Pursuit of Justice*, ed. Robert Francis Kennedy and Theodore J. Lowi (Harper & Row, 1964), 68-69.

and the lynching of Mashal Khan show that something is not right with Pakistan and its society. Once considered tolerant, society has become intolerant². The examination of Pakistan's seventy-five years of history reveals two recurring themes that shaped the country's identity: a strong affinity for its Islamic heritage and a focus on safeguarding itself from its neighbours. The religious leadership is hailed as the guardian of Islamic nationalism and tradition, while the military is regarded as the defender against threats. The partnership of religious faction and military has been cited to forge a unique ideology of Pakistan where Pakistan is an Islamic state with its armed forces defenders of faith³. For that reason, Islam has been used to justify acts in Pakistan, which can be attributed to extremism. However, are there any other factors except blaming everything on religion?

This paper examines the trajectory of extremism within Pakistan. This paper elucidates the factors that facilitated the genesis and proliferation of extremism in Pakistan and its surrounding territories through historical events. Via a systemic exploration, the paper endeavours to offer an exhaustive assessment of the complex interplay between regional, national, and international dynamics that have perpetuated a cycle of violence within the region. This narrative construct would help map out the historical landscape of extremism, often associated with violence, and analyse the underpinning and ramifications of such extremism within a broader geopolitical context.

In the case of Pakistan and especially in Punjab and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, domestic and external factors have contributed to the rise of extremism. This paper focuses on deciphering the social and political root causes of extremism, discussing the social and political factors related to extremism and terrorism in Pakistan by studying these factors in the provinces of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Punjab. It analyses the specific examples of events of historical significance attributed to extremism and its persistence despite several government interventions.

Extremism in Pakistan: Deciphering root causes

Scholars have identified that extremism in Pakistan is marked by several factors that are deeply rooted within its socio-political and economic settings. The factors for the persistence of extremism have been highlighted to include religious ideologies and fundamentalisms⁴, transnational

² Muhammad Hanif, "Pakistan, land of the intolerant," *The New York Times*, November 19 2017, <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/10/19/opinion/pakistan-muslims-ahmadis.html>.

³ Husain Haqqani, *Pakistan: Between mosque and military* (Lahore: Vanguard Books, 2005).

⁴ Khaled Ahmad, *Pakistan's Terror Conundrum* (Penguin Books India, 2021).

networks of extremist organisations^{5 6}, militarism and political violence^{7 8}, youth unemployment and social inequalities^{9 10}, governance issues¹¹ and religious disparity¹².

Basit argues that terrorism and extremism in Pakistan are intertwined, making it challenging to control terrorism without addressing the threat of extremism¹³. As a result, he argues that when formulating any policy, it is crucial to neutralise extremist elements to combat terrorist organisations. Additionally, harming the membership and stifling internal support from local sympathisers is a powerful counter-extremism technique. Although many efforts have been focused on the military solution or hard measures, their short-term gain, nevertheless, soft measures must be used in parallel if long-term success is to be attained¹⁴.

This paper argues that the significant factor for the rise of extremism is identity crises, where Pakistan has seen a surge in extremist movements that have religious, ethnic, and ethno-nationalist outlooks^{15 16}. Due to this, various groups are spreading their ideology instead of forging a common

⁵ Hassan Abbas, *The Taliban Revival: Violence and Extremism on the Pakistan-Afghanistan Frontier* (Yale University Press, 2015).

⁶ Umbreen Javaid, "Partnership in War on Terror and Mounting Militant Extremism in Pakistan," *South Asian Studies* 26, no. 2 (2011), https://pu.edu.pk/images/journal/csas/PDF/V_26_No_2_1Dr.%20Umbreen%20Javaid.pdf.

⁷ Jawad Syed et al., eds., *Faith-Based Violence and Deobandi Militancy in Pakistan* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2016).

⁸ Katarzyna Jasko et al., "A comparison of political violence by left-wing, right-wing, and Islamist extremists in the United States and the world," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 119, no. 30 (2022), <https://doi.org/doi:10.1073/pnas.2122593119>, <https://www.pnas.org/doi/abs/10.1073/pnas.2122593119>.

⁹ Hedieh Mirahmadi et al., *Empowering Pakistan's Civil Society to Counter Global Violent Extremism*, The Brookings (The Brookings, 2015), <https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/Empowering-Pakistans-Civil-Society-to-Counter-Violent-Extremism-English.pdf>.

¹⁰ Lydia Lafoz Ortín, Claudia Pérez Forniés, and Marcos Sanso-Navarro, "Horizontal inequality and conflict: An empirical assessment," *SSRN* (2022), 4165083.

¹¹ John Idriss Lahai et al., eds., *Governance and Political Adaptation in Fragile States* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2019).

¹² Areej Ajmal, "Unraveling The Nexus: Religious Extremism And Sectarian Divide In Pakistan," *Journal Of Climate and Community Development* 2, no. 2 (2023).

¹³ Abdul Basit, "Countering Violent Extremism: Evaluating Pakistan's Counter-Radicalization and De-radicalization Initiatives," *IPRI XV*, no. 2 (2015), <https://ipripak.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/3-art-s-15.pdf>.

¹⁴ Basit, "Countering Violent Extremism: Evaluating Pakistan's Counter-Radicalization and De-radicalization Initiatives."

¹⁵ Farhan Siddiqi, *The Politics of Ethnicity in Pakistan: The Baloch, Sindhi and Mohajir Ethnic Movements* (Oxford: Routledge, 2012).

¹⁶ Farhan Zahid, *The Roots Of Violent Islamic Activism In South Asia* (Narratives, 2014).

culture and nationalist ideology. Another major factor is the role of political and religious leaders who have been playing the Islam card for their agenda^{17 18}.

This study has analysed political, geostrategic, and security drivers and socio-economic drivers of extremism applicable in Pakistan's context.

Political elements

Jinnah's speeches declared Pakistan a modern democratic state based on Islamic principles. Maulana Shabir Usmani, a leader from the Islamist party Jamiat Ulama Islam (JUI), claimed that Pakistan was an Islamic state with sovereign authority exercised within limits prescribed by God.¹⁹ Ordinary folk, too, felt that their newly founded nation was an Islamic state "in a fashion unique in the modern world"²⁰ and their contribution to the Muslim world made them different. The mutual feeling existed that "The Islamic state is the ideal to which Pakistan"²¹ should aspire to become. It was thought crucial to convey to the world that "The demand that Pakistan should be an Islamic state has been a Muslim way of saying that Pakistan should build for itself a good society"²². In the attainment of the Islamic state, Pakistan underwent successive constitutions to make it more Islamic. The confusion persists whether Pakistan is a secular democracy or an Islamic state. Its current constitution, although not in a form that would justify it being called Islamic, has elements that are enough to appease the commoner and the proponents of an Islamic state.

Devji furthers this argument that Pakistan has been a product of Islamic political ideology and favours membership based on the idea of belonging, disregarding ethnicity, and forging a new nationality²³. Ayesha Jalal argues that Pakistan's historical identity had been carved to give it a distinctive appearance of being an Islamic state. Even Jinnah claimed that "Pakistan has been there for centuries... it is there today, and it will remain till the end of the world. It was taken away from us"²⁴. Paracha advances this argument that Pakistanis identify themselves as Muslim first and Pakistani later due to Islamist ideology, codified in constitutions and laws. Hussain argues that the concept of Islamic identity, associated governance and Pakistan ideology influence the relationship between the state and the citizen. He further contends that politico-religious leaders have been "casting Pakistan as the citadel of Islam", using this ideology "as the protective firewall against both real and perceived enemies of Islam and of Pakistan". Identity politics fosters greater friction and contestation among ethnic, social, religious, and economic groupings, intensifying violence. Indeed, Pakistan's unrelenting violence often stems from narrow views of the community and an increasing gap between the governing and the governed.

¹⁷ Kashif Hussain, "From pulpit to marketplace: The evolution of religious political parties in Pakistan," *World Affairs* 187, no. 2 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1002/waf2.12021>, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/waf2.12021>.

¹⁸ Haroon K. Ullah, *Vying for Allah's Vote: Understanding Islamic parties, political violence, and extremism in Pakistan* (Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press, 2014).

¹⁹ Government of Pakistan, *The Constituent Assembly of Pakistan Debates*, (Karachi 1949).

²⁰ W.C. Smith, *Islam in Modern History* (Princeton University Press, 1957), 215.

²¹ Smith, *Islam in Modern History*, 238.

²² Smith, *Islam in Modern History*, 239.

²³ Faisal Devji, *Muslim Zion* (Harvard University Press, 2013).

²⁴ Ayesha Jalal, *The struggle for Pakistan: A Muslim homeland and global politics* (The Belknap Press, 2014), 10.

Saadia Toor has studied the complex interplay of culture, politics, and religion in forming national identity in Pakistan²⁵. She argues that Pakistan's foray into religious extremism is due to its emphasis on being an exclusive religious nationalism, disregarding the social and cultural aspects of its constituent parts. She points out that Islamists overcame the liberal and progressive forces, who favoured the creation of an Islamic State and promoted religious rights within Pakistani society, causing a spike in extremism²⁶. The religious right-wing leadership strived for a Pakistan where "Islamic order and social justice will win the battle against those who want to make Pakistan a secular, socialist state"²⁷. Asma Jahangir, a lawyer and a prominent human rights activist, pungently pointed out that "Past experience has shown that the Islamists gain space when civilian authority weakens... The proliferation of arms and official sanction for jihad have made militant groups a frightening challenge for the government. Pakistan's future remains uncertain, and its will to fight against rising religious intolerance is waning"²⁸.

Blom identified six varieties of factors or 'key mutations' in Pakistan's religious-political environment²⁹. First, state-sponsored religiously motivated moral policing of the public results in a more volatile pattern of religious leadership. Second, political and religious leaders are reluctant to allow a public voice in religious matters due to high illiteracy rates. With rising rates of religious school enrolment, permitting the right to question religious authority is seldom encouraged. Third, with modern communication technology and mass education in religious seminaries and private Islamic schools, there has been competition among religious scholars to attract people to their way of thinking—a competition leading to public appearances in higher frequency. Fourth, mass emigration (from rural to urban zones due to high unemployment rates) has created a new class of rural-educated preachers who have now taken over the urban areas. This has promoted a dangerous conflict of interest among their co-educators. Fifth, the brutal and violent strain exhibited by the religious student wing of a significant religious political party has now taken root, and acceptance in jihadi organisations (including the sectarian outfits) has created an opportunity for the less educated to be taken advantage of under the guise of 'Islamic Street Power.' Moreover, finally, the slogans of 'Islam in Danger' and 'Western Hegemony designed to enslave the Muslim Ummah' have never lost currency. With Hindu-centric (India has been synonymous with Hindu culture) state-backed policies, the public prefers to accept politico-religious leadership³⁰.

As the relationship between the state and society deteriorates, disillusionment with the state opens the door for non-state actors, including extremists, to establish alternative governance systems,

²⁵ Saadia Toor, *The State of Islam: Culture and Cold War Politics in Pakistan* (Pluto Press, 2011).

²⁶ Toor, *The State of Islam: Culture and Cold War Politics in Pakistan*.

²⁷ Ian Buruma, "A Nation Divided," *New York Times Magazine*, January 15 1989, 6, <https://www.nytimes.com/1989/01/15/magazine/a-nation-divided.html>.

²⁸ Asma Jahangir, "Pakistan's Tenets of the Faith," *New Statesman*, April 14, 2011, 2011.

²⁹ Amélie Blom, "Changing Religious Leadership in Contemporary Pakistan: The Case of the Red Mosque," in *Pakistan and Its Diaspora: Multidisciplinary Approaches*, ed. Marta Bolognani and Stephen M. Lyon (New York: Palgrave Macmillan US, 2011).

³⁰ Blom, "Changing Religious Leadership in Contemporary Pakistan: The Case of the Red Mosque," 131-43.

providing justice, security and service delivery³¹. In Pakistan's case, extremist organisations have exploited the unmet needs of the public to garner public support and recruit followers³². State-led efforts to promote Islam (in the form of state-sponsored Islamization) have blurred the line between Sharia and the Constitution, making the political ideology of religious extremism appealing to those who prioritize Islam over Pakistan and its Constitution³³.

Pakistan's history is marred by political crises that disrupt peaceful and harmonious values. Waseem believes that a widespread lack of faith in political leadership and institutions creates an environment where the calls for where the calls of extremist and radical measures gain increased attraction³⁴. This scenario provides fertile ground for the flourishing of radicalism and extremism.

The analysis of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (then North West Frontier Province till 2010) government's action in the terrorist environment of the three regimes of Muttahida Majlis Amal (MMA)³⁵, Awami National Party (ANP)³⁶ and Pakistan Tehrik Insaf (PTI)³⁷, from 2004 to 2018, shows a different thinking pattern by each government³⁸. According to MMA, ensuring excellent governance and accountability by devout and truthful leadership led by Islamic scholars or activists would foster an environment that would lessen the social and political space available for militancy and insurrection. The root causes of terrorism in KP during that era included the US drone assaults in FATA. This Red Mosque Islamabad operation exacerbated the insurgency crisis, the trickle-down of terrorism from Afghanistan, and the resulting implications of the acts of North Atlantic Treaty Organization forces there. Although ANP came under threat from the TTP³⁹, they still tried to counter terrorism by creating Local Peace Committees (LPCs), which were only effective in certain areas, such as Dir and Buner. The ANP also focused on enhancing the KP police's

³¹ Amir Rana and Safdar Sial, *Pakistan's Evolving Militant Landscape: State Responses and Policy options*, Pak Institute for Peace Studies (PIPS) (Islamabad, 2024), https://www.pakpips.com/web/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Final-Report_RNE_withtitlesandmaps-.pdf.

³² Muhammad Amir Rana, "Threat of Religious Extremism," in *Pakistan: The Search for Stability*, ed. Maleeha Lodhi (Hurst Publishers, 2024).

³³ Rana, "Threat of Religious Extremism."

³⁴ Muhammad Waseem, *Political Conflict in Pakistan* (Hurst, 2021).

³⁵ MMA comprised a mixed band of religious parties, Deobandi JUI (F and S); the modernizing JI; the sufi-oriented Bareilvi party, the JUP; Jamiat Ahle Hadith, Wahhabi, or Salafi party; and Islami Tehrik Pakistan, the Shia party.

³⁶ A Pushtun ethno-nationalist party was founded by Khan Abdul Wali Khan (1917-2006), son of Khan Abdul Ghaffar Khan, a Pashtun leader known as Sarhadi Gandhi for his non-violence movement

³⁷ Pakistan Tehrik Insaf (Pakistan Movement for Justice) party was founded by Imran Khan (born in 1952), a former cricketer, in 1996

³⁸ Muhammad Quraish and Fakhrul Islam, "Peace-making Efforts in KP: An Analysis of MMA, ANP and PTI Governments (2002-18)," *Policy Perspectives: The Journal of the Institute of Policy Studies* 15, no. 3 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.13169/polipers.15.3.0197>.

³⁹ Tehrik Taliban Pakistan (Pakistan Student Movement) is an umbrella organization composed of various Islamist militant groups formed in South Waziristan by Baitullah Mehsud in 2007. See Farhat Taj, Amir Mir Monal Kawal Sheikh

capabilities to transform them into a front-line counterterrorism force⁴⁰. On the other hand, PTI took legislative measures and passed laws that they deemed effective in reducing the gap between the citizens and states, not allowing the social and political space to be occupied by terrorists. However, the analysis of these efforts shows that the success of these actions was not only dependent on the political will and acceptance of conflict resolution but also the peace process was often disturbed by TTP wanting to gain more concessions and space for their agenda of implementing sharia⁴¹.

It has been an acknowledged fact that since 9/11, Punjab has seen less violence against the state institutions compared to the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and the former Federally Administered Tribal Area⁴². However, Punjab has witnessed the rise of sectarian violence since the 1980s, from clashes between Shia and Sunni sects of Islam to the current Barelvi brand of Islamic extremism^{43 44}. Abu Zahab contends that Punjab has always been the epicentre of religiously motivated movements and the presence of many sects such as Deobandi, Ahl Hadees, Shia, Brelvi, and even the jihadi groups that operate in the jihadi landscape of dispute land of Kashmir⁴⁵. Although the Sunni sects, along with the Shia, tried to ban the Ahmadiyya community members, they went against each other, as predicted by the Munir report, with the inclusion of Section 295 (C) of the Pakistan Procedure. The rise of militant activities in Punjab, especially by the religiously affiliated organisations in the 1980s, was in response to domestic and international developments. On the domestic front, the Zia administration fully supported the elements that were active participants in his Islamization policy, leading to the politicisation of religion⁴⁶. The centre of such activities was Punjab as, after the death of Zia, most of the militant outfits had their active presence there, Tehrik Taliban Pakistan (TTP) being the only exception. Lashkar-e-Jhangvi (LeJ), Lashkar-e-Tayyiba (LeT), Sipah-e-Sahaba (SSP), Sipah Muhammad (SM), and their antagonist Fiqa-e- Nifaz-e- Jaffaria were created out of circumstances. Some of them had state patronage at such a level that General Zia personally intervened in the release of the head of the militant sectarian group by calling an assistant superintendent of police to release him^{47 48}.

⁴⁰ Quraish and Islam, "Peace-making Efforts in KP: An Analysis of MMA, ANP and PTI Governments (2002-18)."

⁴¹ Quraish and Islam, "Peace-making Efforts in KP: An Analysis of MMA, ANP and PTI Governments (2002-18)."

⁴² Khan Zeb and Zahid Shahab Ahmed, "Structural Violence and Terrorism in the Federally Administered Tribal Areas of Pakistan," *Civil Wars* 21, no. 1 (2019/01/02 2019), <https://doi.org/10.1080/13698249.2019.1586334>.

⁴³ Mujahid Husain, *Punjabi Taliban: Driving Extremism in Pakistan* (Pentagon Press, 2012).

⁴⁴ Syed et al., *Faith-Based Violence and Deobandi Militancy in Pakistan*.

⁴⁵ Mariam Abou Zahab, *Pakistan: A Kaleidoscope of Islam* (Hurst, 2020).

⁴⁶ Arshi Saleem Hashmi, "Historical Roots of the Deobandi Version of Jihadism and Its Implications for Violence in Today's Pakistan," in *Faith-Based Violence and Deobandi Militancy in Pakistan*, ed. Jawad Syed et al. (Palgrave Macmillan, 2016).

⁴⁷ Sher Ali Khan, Shakeel Ahmed, and Fareedullah Chaudhry, "Punjab's 'encounters' with sectarianism," *Herald*, 2016, <https://herald.dawn.com/news/print/1153564>.

⁴⁸ Tariq Khosa, "The miasma of hate," Opinion, *Dawn* (Islamabad), December 5 2015, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1224243>.

Although Punjab had witnessed a series of religiously motivated sectarian assassinations in the 1980s, the Government of Punjab was not equipped to handle these cases as extremist attacks but rather dealt with them as murders. The political scenario required these militant organisations' support in underdeveloped areas, and conflict between various sects had already been established⁴⁹⁵⁰. Hansen warned that in Punjab, radical and extreme Islamist movements have gained significant ground⁵¹. While terrorist acts have decreased, violent sectarianism and crime have increased, with trends of increasingly experiencing radical and even extremist interpretations of Islam being observed, potentially signalling Punjab to be a hotbed of further radicalisation. He further warned that, without any effective government action, the situation was ripe for social discontent, giving rise to a severe crisis resulting in security challenges for the Pakistani state and citizens⁵².

Geostrategy and Security factors

Afzal overviews Pakistan's relationship with extremism by carefully examining survey data, in-depth interviews, historical narrative reporting, and her intuitive grasp of the nation⁵³. She identifies two pillars—Pakistan's place in the Islamic world and Pakistan's rivalry with India—on which Pakistan's passion for extremism is built.

Hasan Abbas gave an outline of the emergence of the Taliban as a violent extremist group close to the Afghanistan–Pakistan borderland and how the populations of both nations influenced the struggle against what is known as Talibanization⁵⁴. However, Ahmed Rashid argues that Pakistanis' extremist ideas were caused by their tense relationship with both the Taliban and the United States of America, commencing with the emergence of militancy in Central Asia and moving towards Afghanistan⁵⁵⁵⁶. He also accuses the governments of both nations of failing to create a plan to combat terrorism in Pakistan and its adjacent nations.

On the international stage, Pakistan has always been portrayed as a Western ally due to its strategic significance and especially its warrior tribes' capacity to produce large numbers of soldiers to fight against anti-Western agendas, especially in the Cold War when it produced anti-Communist warriors⁵⁷ and later become a base and training ground for international jihad⁵⁸. This point was made more significant when the then President of Pakistan, in the Cold War, applied the logic of

⁴⁹ Khan, Ahmed, and Chaudhry, "Punjab's 'encounters' with sectarianism."

⁵⁰ "Pakistan's Hafiz Saeed: Is 'charity leader' linked to Kashmir attacks?," (Online Article), British Broadcasting Corporation News, 2017, accessed 10 October, 2023, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-38596301>.

⁵¹ David Hansen, *The threat of growing extremism in Punjab*, Norwegian Peacebuilding Resource Centre (2012), <https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/156609/0b5ea152f1a7a2e9f40be540e08a4484.pdf>.

⁵² Hansen, *The threat of growing extremism in Punjab*.

⁵³ Madiha Afzal, book *Pakistan Under Siege: Extremism, Society, and the State*, Illustrated ed. (Brookings Institution Press, 2018).

⁵⁴ Abbas, *The Taliban Revival: Violence and Extremism on the Pakistan-Afghanistan Frontier*.

⁵⁵ Ahmed Rashid, *Descent into Chaos: The United States and the Failure of Nation Building in Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Central Asia*, First Edition ed. (Viking, 2008).

⁵⁶ Ahmed Rashid, *Pakistan on the Brink: The Future of America, Pakistan, and Afghanistan*, First Edition ed. (Viking, 2012).

⁵⁷ Husain Haqqani, *Reimagining Pakistan: Transforming a Dysfunctional Nuclear State* (HarperCollins India, 2020).

⁵⁸ Rohan Gunaratna and Khuram Iqbal, *Pakistan: Terrorism Ground Zero* (2011).

unique geo-strategic location owing to being close to Soviet Russia's southern frontier, a common border with China and vital for the global peace that Pakistan remained strong and stable⁵⁹.

Scholars argue that when governments support extremist groups or use extremist rhetoric to advance their interests, it can create an environment where extremism is seen as legitimate and acceptable^{60 61}. Cohan⁶², Khan and Zhaoying⁶³, and Khan⁶⁴ have found that state sponsorship of extremist groups can create an environment in which extremist ideas are normalised and the barriers to recruitment are lowered.

On multiple occasions, India has accused Pakistan of supporting cross-border extremist organisations, especially in the disputed land of Jammu and Kashmir⁶⁵. Afghanistan has been voicing its concern; even its once ally emirate of Afghanistan, run by the Taliban, has asked to look into itself rather than point fingers⁶⁶. Pakistan has also accused India of sponsoring the ethnonationalism movements in Pakistan and Afghanistan of harbouring anti-state elements and giving them safe passage. The border towns near the border, especially near Afghanistan, have been a hotbed for extremists.

The wave of cross-border violence and extremism in the Afghanistan-Pakistan border and strategic depth policy began under the guise of granting independence to Pashtuns. The main aim was that those living in the Northwest Frontier Province should either be granted freedom or merge with Afghanistan, later known as the Pashtunistan movement⁶⁷, the brainchild of the Prime Minister of Afghanistan, Sardar Muhammad Daoud Khan⁶⁸, in the 1960s.

Due to linguistic and ethnic similarities across borders, the issue has changed from merging cultures to implementing sharia law across the country. The historical analysis shows that both countries tried to influence each other. However, the Soviet-Afghan War created fissures that allowed the extremists access to public sentiment and spread their ideology.

⁵⁹ Mohammed Ayub Khan, "The Pakistan-American Alliance: Stresses and Strains," *Foreign Affairs*, 1964.

⁶⁰ Brittnee Carter, Maya Van Nuys, and Cagil Albayrak, "State sponsorship of religiously motivated terrorism: A deadly combination," *Democracy and Security* 17, no. 2 (2021).

⁶¹ Brittnee Carter, "When civilians are targets: The fatal effects of state sponsored religiously motivated terrorism," *Democracy and Security* 18, no. 1 (2022).

⁶² John Alan Cohan, "Formulation of a State's Response to Terrorism and State-Sponsored Terrorism," *Peace International Law Review* 14, no. 1 (2002), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.58948/2331-3536.1189>.

⁶³ Akbar Khan and Han Zhaoying, "Conflict escalation in the Middle East revisited: thinking through interstate rivalries and state-sponsored terrorism," *Israel Affairs* 26, no. 2 (2020).

⁶⁴ Akbar Khan, "Steps-to-War Theory and Interstate Wars in the Middle East: Is State-Sponsored Terrorism Another Escalating Step?," *Journal of Asian and African Studies* 56, no. 7 (2021).

⁶⁵ Daniel Byman, "Understanding, and misunderstanding, state sponsorship of terrorism," *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 45, no. 12 (2022).

⁶⁶ Rashid, *Descent into Chaos: The United States and the Failure of Nation Building in Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Central Asia*.

⁶⁷ T. Devasher, *The Pashtuns: A Contested History* (HarperCollins, 2022).

⁶⁸ A prince of the Royal family of Afghanistan (1909-1978), he served as Prime Minister (1960-1963) and later the first President of Afghanistan after his coup d'état against the monarchy in 1973. Assassinated in the Saur Revolution by Communists in 1978.

Jalal, tracing the history of jihadi leadership and movements in South Asia, argues that the concept of jihad in South Asia has "gone from being the core ethical principle of Islam to becoming a justification for unethical actions, in pursuit of worldly aims"⁶⁹. Abou Zahab notes that there have been three elements that allowed for extremism and radicalisation in the name of Islam in areas that were bordering Afghanistan or Kashmir⁷⁰. According to her, one element was the initiative of movements by young militants who participated in jihad, the second was the development of extremist movements by security agencies in Pakistan that aimed for international jihad, and the last element was the rise of militant wings of politico-religious parties for the protection of their interests.

Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto was the architect of Pakistan's policy of creating the first batch of Mujahideen when he established the Afghan Cell in Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI) and Foreign Office. His support of Afghan militant groups to counter Daoud Khan's government bore fruit when the Soviets invaded Afghanistan in December 1979. Bhutto started supporting those elements that were not only against the Daoud regime but that could be used as an asset to Pakistan's interest when required. Bhutto's strategy was that: "Two can play at the same game. . . . We know where their weak points are, just as they know ours. The non-Pushtuns there hate Pushtun domination. So we have our ways of persuading Daoud not to aggravate our problems"⁷¹. Islamabad's plan for waging a secret war on Afghanistan through proxy was divided into many plans. One was increasing intelligence collecting in that country, which included identifying potential Afghan friends and weaknesses. The most significant strategy, however, was to build an insurgent army from the swelling number of anti-Daoud Afghan refugees in Pakistan⁷². Acting through its intelligence agency, Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI), it was particularly interested in a tiny group of former students, university professors, and intellectuals who advocated for the agendas of Egypt's Muslim Brotherhood and Pakistan's Jamat Islami. Many future Afghan rebel commanders and political figures were to be included in this group, including Ahmed Shah Massoud, Burhanuddin Rabbani, Sibghatullah Mojadeddi, Gulbuddin Hekmatyar, Jaleleddin Haqqani, and Abd al-Rasul Sayyaf.

Pakistan has seen an increase in terrorist attacks since the Afghan Taliban seized the government in Kabul in 2021, particularly in its border regions, where a 2014 incursion targeted TTP bases. According to a United Nations Security Council report, up to 4,000 TTP fighters are positioned over the border in Afghanistan. In June 2024, Pakistan announced its renewed plan to counter terrorism and extremism in Azm-e-Istehkam (Vying for Stability), with confusion surrounding it. The Prime Minister called it the Vision, while for the military, it is still part of the National Action Plan through kinetic and non-kinetic measures, such as operations like previous ones⁷³. It is yet

⁶⁹ Ayesha Jalal, *Partisans of Allah: Jihad in South Asia* (Harvard University Press, 2008), 300.

⁷⁰ Abou Zahab, *Pakistan: A Kaleidoscope of Islam*.

⁷¹ Diego Cordovez and Selig S. Harrison, *Out of Afghanistan: The inside story of the Soviet withdrawal* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1995), 61.

⁷² Haqqani, *Pakistan: Between mosque and military*.

⁷³ "Azm-e-Istehkam not a 'large-scale military operation,' clarifies PM Sharif amid growing criticism," Arab News Pakistan, 2024, accessed July 15, 2024, <https://www.arabnews.pk/node/2537021/pakistan>.

to be seen if the integrated approach to counter terrorism and extremism envisioned in the Azme-e-Istehkam bears fruit.

After decades of strife, Pakistani policymakers voiced the hope that regional dynamics would alter in the months following the onset of the Taliban rule. However, many critics and academics are calling for Pakistan to focus on the issues that give rise to extremism, poverty, political instability, and religious polarities. Taliban government's Foreign Minister quipped, "The current problems of Pakistan are the result of the mistakes of the Pakistani government"⁷⁴. As countering extremism requires all-out effort by the state and citizens, the mistakes can only be amended by cooperation.

Socio-economic drivers

The population becomes vulnerable to an extremist ideology when a sizeable part lacks access to basic social needs and economic resources, leading to poor living conditions and eventually developing a sense of deprivation. In this situation, the only way out for many people is to join the violent extremist group for better prospects of livelihood⁷⁵. According to the United Nations Development Programme, in countries with high levels of inequality, people are more likely to feel that the political and economic systems are rigged against them, that their voices are not heard, and that the institutions of democracy are failing them, which fosters conditions for extremist movements to gain hold⁷⁶. It is further argued that there is a strong correlation between socioeconomic exclusion, inequality, and the likelihood of individuals joining extremist groups⁷⁷. Socioeconomic marginalisation is a crucial driver of violent extremism, particularly in contexts where poverty and inequality levels are high^{78 79 80}. Socioeconomic marginalisation can create a sense of hopelessness and alienation among individuals and communities, leading to frustration, anger, and disillusionment with the existing political and social order^{81 82 83}. In such contexts,

⁷⁴ "After Peshawar Blast, Muttaqi Says Pakistan Should Not Blame Others," Tolo News, updated February 1 2023, 2023, <https://tolonews.com/afghanistan-181858>.

⁷⁵ UNDP, *Preventing and Responding to Violent Extremism in Africa: A Development Approach* (New York, 2015).

⁷⁶ UNDP, *Preventing Violent Extremism Through Promoting Inclusive Development, Tolerance And Respect For Diversity* (2016).

⁷⁷ UNDP, *Preventing and Responding to Violent Extremism in Africa: A Development Approach*.

⁷⁸ Kamaldeep Bhui, Nasir Warfa, and Edgar Jones, "Is Violent Radicalisation Associated with Poverty, Migration, Poor Self-Reported Health and Common Mental Disorders?," *PLoS ONE* 9, no. 3 (2014), <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0090718>, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0090718>.

⁷⁹ Corinne Graff, "Poverty, Development, and Violent Extremism in Weak States," in *Confronting poverty : weak states and U.S. national security*, ed. Susan E. Rice, Corinne Graff, and Carlos Pascual (Washington, DC: The Brookings Institution, 2010).

⁸⁰ Susan E. Rice, "Poverty and State Weakness," in *Confronting poverty : weak states and U.S. national security*, ed. Susan E. Rice, Corinne Graff, and Carlos Pascual (Washington, DC: The Brookings Institution, 2010).

⁸¹ T. Krieger and D. Meierrieks, "Income Inequality, Redistribution and Domestic Terrorism," *World Development* 116 (2019), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.12.008>.

⁸² Nicholas Sambanis, "Poverty and the Organization of Political Violence: A Review and Some Conjectures" (Brookings Trade Forum 2004, Washington, DC, Brookings Institution, 2005).

⁸³ Susan E. Rice, Corinne Graff, and Janet Lewis, *Poverty and Civil War: What Policymakers Need to Know*, Brookings (2006).

violent extremist groups may exploit the grievances of marginalised communities, presenting themselves as a practical alternative to the status quo and offering the promise of economic, social, and political change⁸⁴.

Farahnaz Ispahani argues that "Pakistan has descended to its current state of religious intolerance through a series of political decisions made by Jinnah's successors".⁸⁵ She advances her argument that the passing of Objective Resolution after Jinnah paved the way for the Islamists. She also mentions the concerns of a leader of a minority religious group about the misuse of blasphemy laws when he "cautioned that tying Islam and politics would weaken reason and curb criticism as far as state policies were concerned"⁸⁶.

Ideological factors, such as religious, ethnic, or nationalist ideologies, can also drive extremism⁸⁷. Some individuals may feel that their religious, ethnic, or national identity is under threat, which can lead to radicalisation and extremist behaviour^{88 89 90}. Extremist groups may exploit these identities and manipulate them to advance their agenda and recruit new members⁹¹. Extremist ideologies, often rooted in distorted interpretations of religious or political doctrines, supply justifications for violent actions^{92 93}. Radical interpretations of religious texts, coupled with a sense of religious duty or righteousness, can fuel the commitment to extremist ideologies^{94 95}. Political ideologies that advocate for revolutionary change or the establishment of a new order also contribute to the micro-level dynamics of violent extremism⁹⁶.

⁸⁴ Alan B. Krueger and Jitka Malec`kova, "Education, Poverty and Terrorism: Is There a Causal Connection?," *Journal of Economic Perspectives* 17, no. 4 (2003), <https://www.sas.rochester.edu/psc/clarke/214/Krueger03.pdf>.

⁸⁵ Farahnaz Ispahani, *Purifying the Land of the Pure Pakistan's Religious Minorities* (Noida, Uttar Pradesh: Harper Collins, 2018), 37.

⁸⁶ Ispahani, *Purifying the Land of the Pure Pakistan's Religious Minorities*, 38.

⁸⁷ W. Koomen and J. V. D. Pligt, *The Psychology of Radicalization and Terrorism* (Routledge, 2016).

⁸⁸ Sherrill W. Hayes, "Changing Radicalization to Resilience by Understanding Marginalization," *Peace Review: A Journal of Social Justice* 29 (2017), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/10402659.2017.1308190>.

⁸⁹ John Pilger, *The New Rulers of the World* (Verso Books, 2016).

⁹⁰ S. Taji-Farouki and B. M. Nafi, *Islamic Thought in the Twentieth Century* (I. B. Tauris, 2004).

⁹¹ Hayes, "Changing Radicalization to Resilience by Understanding Marginalization."

⁹² Randy Borum, "Radicalization into Violent Extremism I: A Review of Social Science Theories," *Journal of Strategic Security* 4, no. 4 (2011), <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26463910>.

⁹³ Arie W. Kruglanski et al., "The Psychology of Radicalization and Deradicalization: How Significance Quest Impacts Violent Extremism," *Political Psychology* 35, no. S1 (2014), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12163>, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/pops.12163>.

⁹⁴ Mohammed Hafez and Creighton Mullins, "The Radicalization Puzzle: A Theoretical Synthesis of Empirical Approaches to Homegrown Extremism," *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 38, no. 11 (2015/11/02 2015), <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610X.2015.1051375>, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610X.2015.1051375>.

⁹⁵ Andrew Silke, "Holy warriors: Exploring the psychological processes of jihadi radicalization," *European Journal of Criminology* 5 (2008), <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477370807084226>.

⁹⁶ Q. Wiktorowicz, *Radical Islam Rising: Muslim Extremism in the West* (Rowman & Littlefield, 2005).

Haque notes that extremism in Pakistan is due to a combination of two interconnected dependent factors: a closed Islamic identity and a reactive Islamic movement⁹⁷. Various surveys show that youth in urban and rural settings think of Islam as the key identity maker and a basis for self and societal improvement^{98 99}. The reactive Islamic movement includes militant, political and missionary organisations. He argues that mainstream Islamic discourse in Pakistan only furthers religious extremism, not limited to militant or terrorist organisations¹⁰⁰. Islamic missionary organisations and religious-political parties also use it to increase their appeal to the masses. Inspired by the Islamic rhetoric, youth attracted towards these organisations have a high chance of becoming an extremist sympathiser if not acting on their violent methods for enforcement of Islam. Any perceived or actual discrimination or marginalisation of ethnic or religious minorities, creating a sense of injustice, humiliation, and alienation among those groups, causes an identity crisis or grievance. The prolonged lack of a solution to identity crises or grievances can be a potent driver of violent extremism, mainly when this phenomenon is exploited by violent extremist groups who claim to be defending the rights and interests of those groups¹⁰¹. The identified crises or grievances are more pronounced in those countries with a distinct ethnic or religious minority that a significant part of the state and nation has marginalised. This leads to insurgency and terrorist activities¹⁰². Schwartz et al. have identified the rise of terrorism in countries facing identity crises and point out that the prevalence of extremism and terrorism “represents the confluence of a cultural identity strongly based in collectivism and fundamentalist adherence to religious or cultural principles, a social identity-based in sharp contrasts between one’s group and groups perceived as threats, and a foreclosed and authoritarian sense of personal identity or, less often, a diffused and aimless personal identity”¹⁰³.

The search for identity and a sense of belonging contributes to violent extremism. Those individuals who experience an identity crisis or feel alienated from their communities may be vulnerable to extremist narratives that provide them with a new identity and a sense of belonging¹⁰⁴

⁹⁷ Raheem ul Haque, "Can Pakistan Have a De- radicalised Future?," in *Rethinking Pakistan*, ed. Bilal Zahoor and Raza Rumi, A 21st Century Perspective (Anthem Press, 2020).

⁹⁸ Raheem ul Haque, *Youth Radicalization in Pakistan*, United States Institute of Peace (February 26, 2014),

https://www.usip.org/sites/default/files/PB%20167_Youth_Radicalization_in_Pakistan.pdf.

⁹⁹ Haque, "Can Pakistan Have a De- radicalised Future?."

¹⁰⁰ Haque, "Can Pakistan Have a De- radicalised Future?."

¹⁰¹ Arun Kundnani and Ben Hayes, *The globalisation of Countering Violent Extremism policies Undermining human rights, instrumentalising civil society*, Transnational Institute (Amsterdam, 2018), https://www.preventwatch.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/014092_26ca35cecec34464a5419fb6e72bf7e9.pdf.

¹⁰² K. Yusoufzai and F. Emmerling, "How identity crisis, relative deprivation, personal characteristics, and empathy contribute to the engagement of Western individuals in Islamist terrorist behavior," *Journal of Terrorism Research* 8, no. 1 (2017), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.15664/jtr.1292>.

¹⁰³ Seth J. Schwartz, Curtis S. Dunkel, and Alan S. Waterman, "Terrorism: An Identity Theory Perspective," *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 32, no. 6 (2009): 537, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10576100902888453>.

¹⁰⁴ Emily Corner et al., "Reviewing the links between violent extremism and personality, personality disorders, and psychopathy," *The Journal of Forensic Psychiatry & Psychology* 32, no. 3

¹⁰⁵. This psychological vulnerability can be exploited by extremist groups looking to recruit and radicalise individuals^{106 107}.

Interdisciplinary academics have tried to address Pakistan's extremist concerns. According to educators, Pakistan's subpar educational system or the difficulty enrolling in school is to blame for the increase in violent extremism^{108 109}. Pakistan's failure to recognise that education is both for development and social justice has led to no choice between these goals. Plans and Policies are frequently drafted with objectives that do not express the aim¹¹⁰. These policies are designed with goals and objectives that often fade into obscurity because they are unreasonable, unattainable, and inflexible regarding progress. This also applies to other services.

Scholars have argued that economic factors, such as poverty, unemployment, and inequality, contribute to extremism¹¹¹. Graff points out that countries with elevated levels of poverty, underdevelopment, and unemployment often engage in violence¹¹². In such circumstances, the most vulnerable section of society is the youth and with a high percentage of the youth population with no avenues for productivity, they are inclined to be fascinated by violent elements that encourage them to spread chaos, thus preventing them from becoming a productive part of the development of the country¹¹³. Poverty and extremism have been linked to a dependent relationship^{114 115}.

(2021/05/04 2021), <https://doi.org/10.1080/14789949.2021.1884736>,
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14789949.2021.1884736>.

¹⁰⁵ F. M. Moghaddam, "The staircase to terrorism: a psychological exploration," *Am Psychol* 60, no. 2 (Feb-Mar 2005), <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066x.60.2.161>.

¹⁰⁶ Shandon Harris-Hogan, Kate Barrelle, and Andrew Zammit, "What is countering violent extremism? Exploring CVE policy and practice in Australia," *Behavioral Sciences of Terrorism and Political Aggression* 8, no. 1 (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1080/19434472.2015.1104710>.

¹⁰⁷ Paul Gill, John Horgan, and Paige Deckert, "Bombing Alone: Tracing the Motivations and Antecedent Behaviors of Lone-Actor Terrorists," *Journal of Forensic Sciences* 59, no. 2 (2014), <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/1556-4029.12312>.

¹⁰⁸ A. Mumtaz, *Continuity and Change in the Traditional System of Islamic Education: The Case of Pakistan* (Karachi: Oxford University Press, 2000).

¹⁰⁹ T. Rahman, *Denizens of Alien Worlds: A Study of Education, Inequality and Polarization in Pakistan* (Karachi: Oxford University Press, 2004).

¹¹⁰ Javed Hasan Aly, Education in Pakistan: a white paper revised document to debate and finalize the national education policy, (Islamabad: National Education Policy Review Team, Ministry of Education, 2007).

¹¹¹ Bhui, Warfa, and Jones, "Is Violent Radicalisation Associated with Poverty, Migration, Poor Self-Reported Health and Common Mental Disorders?."

¹¹² Graff, "Poverty, Development, and Violent Extremism in Weak States."

¹¹³ Rice, "Poverty and State Weakness."

¹¹⁴ Aniruddha Bagchi and Jomon A Paul, "Youth unemployment and terrorism in the MENAP (Middle East, North Africa, Afghanistan, and Pakistan) region," *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences* 64 (2018).

¹¹⁵ Christopher Blattman and Edward Miguel, "Civil War," *Journal of Economic Literature* 48, no. 1 (2010), <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.48.1.3>, <https://www.aeaweb.org/articles?id=10.1257/jel.48.1.3>.

However, scholars have refuted this as a weak link when studied in Pakistan^{116 117}. However, the fact cannot be ignored that people experiencing poverty are the prime target of militants and extremists because of limited avenues for them to access social mobility^{118 119}.

When the state fails to provide critical services, Islamist organisations, particularly those inspired by Deobandi and Wahhabi doctrines, acquire influence and provide social services to the public. In Punjab, these organisations involve a few outlawed jihadi factions, including Lashkar-e-Jhangvi (LeJ), Lashkar-e-Tayyiba (LeT), Sipah-e-Sahaba (SSP), and Jama'at ud-Dawa (JuD), the disputed parent organisation of LeT. Many of these groups have sub-organisations that provide welfare services. Their charity activities include providing clothing, food and presents to celebrate holidays, as well as setting up religious seminaries (madaris) for students who cannot afford conventional education. In return, these organisations provide logistical, intellectual, and human resources for the jihadi and extremist elements. Iannaccone and Berman argue that “radical Islamist groups have enjoyed broad support—especially among the poorer segments of society—because they are major suppliers of mutual aid and social service”¹²⁰.

The acceptance of extremist ideology has crept into the social fabric of the state and society. The killing of the then Governor of Punjab, Salman Taseer, in 2011 by his police bodyguard, Mumtaz Qadri, outside a restaurant in Islamabad, was one incident that has proved that point. Qadri was given the death penalty, and many followers of the Brelvi Sect attended his funeral procession and his first death anniversary and breathed a new life into the secluded and docile Brelvi movement. This movement turned violent, giving birth to a politico-religious entity now called Tehrik-Labaik-Ya-Rasoolullah (TYLR). Many followers of this new brand of extremists are simple folks who show the same traits as demonstrated by the Majlis Ahrar. The conflict between the Ahmadiyya religious community¹²¹ and Majlis Ahrar Islam¹²² (Council of Freeman of Islam) or simply Ahrar (Freemen), a politico-religious organisation, had been brewing since the 1920s.

¹¹⁶ Graeme Blair et al., "Poverty and Support for Militant Politics: Evidence from Pakistan," *American Journal of Political Science* 57, no. 1 (2013), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2012.00604.x>, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2012.00604.x>.

¹¹⁷ Carol Christine Fair et al., "Relative Poverty, Perceived Violence, and Support for Militant Politics: Evidence from Pakistan," *Political Science Research and Methods* 6, no. 1 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1017/psrm.2016.6>, <https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/3AEAF20C324355E612F10AF59BC1DC38>.

¹¹⁸ Shehzad H Qazi, "Rebels of the frontier: origins, organization, and recruitment of the Pakistani Taliban," *Small Wars & Insurgencies* 22, no. 4 (2011).

¹¹⁹ Carol Christine Fair, "Militant recruitment in Pakistan: A new look at the militancy–madrasah connection," in *Pakistan's Political Labyrinths* (Routledge India, 2015).

¹²⁰ Laurence R Iannaccone and Eli Berman, "Religious extremism: The good, the bad, and the deadly," *Public choice* 128 (2006): 119.

¹²¹ Officially, the Ahmadiyya Muslim Jama'at (AMJ), a messianic movement within Islam, originated in British India. It was founded by Mirza Ghulam Ahmad (1835-1908) as a reformation movement, later reincarnation of Mahdi and then Prophet. See S.R. Valentine, *Islam and the Ahmadiyya Jama'at: History, Belief, Practice* (Hurst & Company, 2008).

¹²² For details on Ahrar, see Samina Awan, *Political Islam in Colonial Punjab: Majlis-i Ahrar 1929-1949* (Oxford University Press, 2010); Tahir Kamran, "Majlis-i-Ahrar-i-Islam: religion, socialism and agitation in action," *South Asian History and Culture* 4, no. 4 (2013/10/01 2013),

It was observed that if "you can persuade the masses to believe that something they are asked to do is religiously right or enjoined by religion, you can set them to any course of action, regardless of all considerations of discipline, loyalty, decency, morality or civic sense"¹²³.

With the country's ever-increasing problem of religious bigotry and violence since the 1980s, many intellectuals, authors, and political historians have blamed the Bhutto government's 1974 act of constitutionally redefining the status of the Ahmadiyya, formerly recognised as a Muslim sect, as the starting point for what began to mutate into a sectarian and religious monstrosity over the next three decades. Many commentators accurately point out that by caving into the religious parties' demands in this situation (especially after they had resorted to violence), Bhutto unknowingly restored their credibility and standing, which had been severely harmed during the 1970 election. Bhutto gained consensus on the constitution, established a very successful Muslim countries' congregation of the Organization of Islamic Countries, and reformed the economy and the administrative setup. However, he could not solve the '90-year-old problem'.¹²⁴ So, as a pragmatist who wanted the support of all factions, Islamic parties, and the Ahmadiya community, he threw the ball into the court of the people's representatives in the Parliament to decide.

Munir Report of 1954 had earlier noted that no two religious leaders would agree on the fundamental question of who would be called a Muslim. Any attempt by one of the religious sects, if differed from the definition and explanation of the other, would deem that sect out of the fold of Islam and may be declared as infidel¹²⁵. The Second Amendment passed on 7th September 1974, amended Articles 106¹²⁶ and 260¹²⁷ of the Constitution of Pakistan, 1973 defined Muslim and answered the Munir Report's query of who is a Muslim.

Zia went further than any of the leadership to incite violence indirectly. He gave an already radicalised society a legal weapon that became a tool for the oppression of minorities and allowed anyone to be targeted. One example is his inclusion of Section 295-C¹²⁸ into the Pakistan Penal

<https://doi.org/10.1080/19472498.2013.824678>, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19472498.2013.824678>;
Tahir Kamran, "The Pre-History of Religious Exclusionism in Contemporary Pakistan: Khatam-e-Nubuwwat 1889–1953," *Modern Asian Studies* 49 (03/11 2015),
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0026749X14000043>; Fatima Z. Rahman, "Pakistan: A Conducive Setting for Islamist Violence Against Ahmadis," in *Faith-Based Violence and Deobandi Militancy in Pakistan*, ed. Jawad Syed et al. (London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2016).

¹²³ Government of Punjab, Report of the Court of Inquiry constituted under Punjab Act II of 1954 to enquire into the Punjab disturbances of 1953, 231 (Lahore: Government of Punjab, 1954).

¹²⁴ Hamid Khan, *Constitutional and Political History of Pakistan*, 3 ed. (Karachi: OUP, 2017).

¹²⁵ Punjab, Short Report of the Court of Inquiry constituted under Punjab Act II of 1954 to enquire into the Punjab disturbances of 1953.

¹²⁶ Article 106 added the words 'and persons of Qadiani group or the Lahori group (who call themselves 'Ahmadis')' in the non-Muslim category for purpose of reserved seats in the provincial assemblies.

¹²⁷ Article 260 reads as 'A person who does not believe in the absolute and unqualified finality of The Prophethood of Muhammad (Peace be upon him), the last of the Prophets or claims to be a Prophet, in any sense of the word or of any description whatsoever, after Muhammad (Peace be upon him), or recognises such a claimant as a Prophet or religious reformer, is not a Muslim for the purposes of the Constitution or law.'

¹²⁸ Section 295C is blasphemy law under the Pakistan Penal Code and read as '295C Use of derogatory remarks, etc. in respect of the Holy Prophet: Whoever by words, either spoken or written, or by

Code, declaring the death penalty as the only punishment for blasphemy against the Prophet (PBUH). Although Section 295-C was hailed as a legislative measure ensuring that "no one would dare to commit blasphemy against the Holy Prophet in the future", the recorded occurrences following its implementation demonstrated its failure. Instead of being a fail-safe safeguard, it has multiplied real and perceived blasphemous content. It has been used so many times since its promulgation that "every accusation and allegation, whether true or false, is repeated and reproduced in newspapers, judicial documents, digital media, and individual conversations, whether genuine or false due to misconceptions, misunderstandings, socio-religious differences, or plain malice"¹²⁹.

With ease of access to social media and no regulatory mechanism at the disposal of the state, it has become easier to accuse someone of blasphemy, punish them and then wait for the state to act. The factory workers lynched a Sri Lankan manager for his alleged blasphemy of requesting them to remove the poster of the TLP-affiliated organisation. In another incident, a student stabbed his teacher for allowing a mixed-gender party in the college and accused the teacher of having made anti-Islamic speeches. The Human Rights Commission, in its annual State of Human Rights Report, mentions that as many as 171 people were accused under the blasphemy laws up until 2022, with sixty-five per cent of cases taking place in Punjab¹³⁰.

Conclusion

Jalal, tracing the history of jihadi leadership and movements in South Asia, argues that the concept of jihad in South Asia has "gone from being the core ethical principle of Islam to becoming a justification for unethical actions, in pursuit of worldly aims". notes that there have been three elements that allowed for extremism and radicalisation in the name of Islam in areas that were bordering Afghanistan or Kashmir. According to her, one element was the initiative of movements by young militants who participated in jihad, the second was the development of extremist movements by security agencies in Pakistan that aimed for international jihad, and the last element was the rise of militant wings of politico-religious parties for the protection of their interests.

In examining the multifaceted nature of extremism in Pakistan, it becomes evident that the roots of this phenomenon are deeply embedded in the country's historical, socioeconomic, and political landscape. The interplay between religious ideologies and national identity has significantly shaped the trajectory of extremism, leading to a persistent cycle of violence and unrest. This paper has highlighted that while religious extremism is often at the forefront of discussions, it is crucial to recognise the broader context in which these ideologies thrive.

visible representation, or by any imputation, innuendo, or insinuation, directly or indirectly, defiles the sacred name of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) shall be punished with death, or imprisonment for life, and shall also be liable to fine.'

¹²⁹ Asad Ahmed, "A brief history of the anti-blasphemy laws," in *Herald* (Dawn Media Group, October 31 2018).

¹³⁰ HRCF, *State of Human Rights in 2022*, Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (2023), <https://hrfp-web.org/hrfpweb/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/2023-State-of-human-rights-in-2022.pdf>. As per the report, the highest register cases of blasphemy were reported from Chiniot, Faisalabad, Gujranwala, Dera Ghazi Khan, Nankana Sahib, Lahore and Sheikhpura

Historically, Pakistan's founding principles as an Islamic state have created a paradox where the very ideology meant to unify the nation has also been a source of division. The politicisation of Islam, particularly during the Zia regime, institutionalised religious extremism and allowed it to permeate various aspects of society. This has resulted in a landscape where extremist narratives are not only accepted but also propagated by influential political and religious leaders. The use of religion as a tool for political gain has further exacerbated the situation, leading to a rise in sectarian violence and intolerance.

Socioeconomic factors play a pivotal role in the rise of extremism as well. High levels of poverty, unemployment, and social inequality create a fertile ground for extremist ideologies to take root. Young people, in particular, are vulnerable to recruitment by extremist groups when they perceive limited opportunities for a better future. The lack of access to education and essential social services further marginalises these individuals, making them susceptible to the allure of extremist narratives that promise empowerment and purpose.

Moreover, identity crises stemming from ethnic and religious marginalisation contribute significantly to the rise of extremist movements. Various groups within Pakistan have increasingly turned to extremist ideologies as a means of asserting their identity and seeking recognition. This fragmentation of national identity undermines the potential for a cohesive national narrative, leading to further polarisation and conflict. The failure of the state to address these grievances has allowed non-state actors to fill the void, often with violent consequences.

The paper also emphasises the role of blasphemy laws, particularly Section 295 (C), in perpetuating a culture of intolerance and violence. The misuse of these laws has led to a climate of fear and has emboldened extremist groups to target individuals accused of blasphemy, further entrenching the cycle of violence. This legal framework not only stifles dissent but also reinforces extremist ideologies by framing them as defenders of faith.

In conclusion, addressing the rise of extremism in Pakistan requires a comprehensive and multifaceted approach. It is essential to move beyond military solutions and focus on long-term strategies that address the root causes of extremism. This includes promoting inclusive governance, enhancing socioeconomic opportunities, and fostering interfaith dialogue to build a more tolerant society. The state must take initiative-taking measures to dismantle the structures that enable extremism to flourish while also engaging civil society in the fight against intolerance. Only through a concerted effort that involves all stakeholders can Pakistan hope to break the cycle of extremism and build a more peaceful and stable future.

Abbas, Hassan. *The Taliban Revival: Violence and Extremism on the Pakistan-Afghanistan Frontier*. Yale University Press, 2015.

Abou Zahab, Mariam. *Pakistan: A Kaleidoscope of Islam*. Hurst, 2020.

Afzal, Madiha. *book Pakistan under Siege: Extremism, Society, and the State*. Illustrated ed.: Brookings Institution Press, 2018.

Ahmad, Khaled. *Pakistan's Terror Conundrum*. Penguin Books India, 2021.

Ahmed, Asad. "A Brief History of the Anti-Blasphemy Laws." In *Herald*, Dawn Media Group, October 31 2018.

Ajmal, Areej. "Unraveling the Nexus: Religious Extremism and Sectarian Divide in Pakistan." *Journal Of Climate and Community Development* 2, no. 2 (2023): 38-47.

- Aly, Javed Hasan. *Education in Pakistan: A White Paper Revised Document to Debate and Finalize the National Education Policy*. Islamabad: National Education Policy Review Team, Ministry of Education, 2007.
- Awan, Samina. *Political Islam in Colonial Punjab: Majlis-I Ahrar 1929-1949*. Oxford University Press, 2010.
- Ayub Khan, Mohammed. "The Pakistan-American Alliance: Stresses and Strains." *Foreign Affairs*, 1964.
- Bagchi, Aniruddha, and Jomon A Paul. "Youth Unemployment and Terrorism in the Menap (Middle East, North Africa, Afghanistan, and Pakistan) Region." *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences* 64 (2018): 9-20.
- Basit, Abdul. "Countering Violent Extremism: Evaluating Pakistan's Counter-Radicalization and De-Radicalization Initiatives." *IPRI XV*, no. 2 (2015): 44-68. <https://ipripak.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/3-art-s-15.pdf>.
- Bhui, Kamaldeep, Nasir Warfa, and Edgar Jones. "Is Violent Radicalisation Associated with Poverty, Migration, Poor Self-Reported Health and Common Mental Disorders?". *PLoS ONE* 9, no. 3 (2014): e90718. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0090718>. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0090718>.
- Blair, Graeme, C. Christine Fair, Neil Malhotra, and Jacob N. Shapiro. "Poverty and Support for Militant Politics: Evidence from Pakistan." *American Journal of Political Science* 57, no. 1 (2013): 30-48. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2012.00604.x>. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2012.00604.x>.
- Blattman, Christopher, and Edward Miguel. "Civil War." *Journal of Economic Literature* 48, no. 1 (2010): 3-57. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.48.1.3>. <https://www.aeaweb.org/articles?id=10.1257/jel.48.1.3>.
- Blom, Amélie. "Changing Religious Leadership in Contemporary Pakistan: The Case of the Red Mosque." In *Pakistan and Its Diaspora: Multidisciplinary Approaches*, edited by Marta Bolognani and Stephen M. Lyon, 135-68. New York: Palgrave Macmillan US, 2011.
- Borum, Randy. "Radicalization into Violent Extremism I: A Review of Social Science Theories." *Journal of Strategic Security* 4, no. 4 (2011): 7-36. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26463910>.
- Buruma, Ian. "A Nation Divided." *New York Times Magazine*, January 15 1989, 6, 27. <https://www.nytimes.com/1989/01/15/magazine/a-nation-divided.html>.
- Byman, Daniel. "Understanding, and Misunderstanding, State Sponsorship of Terrorism." *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 45, no. 12 (2022): 1031-49.
- Carter, Brittnee. "When Civilians Are Targets: The Fatal Effects of State Sponsored Religiously Motivated Terrorism." *Democracy and Security* 18, no. 1 (2022): 26-50.
- Carter, Brittnee, Maya Van Nuys, and Cagil Albayrak. "State Sponsorship of Religiously Motivated Terrorism: A Deadly Combination." *Democracy and Security* 17, no. 2 (2021): 181-209.
- Cohan, John Alan. "Formulation of a State's Response to Terrorism and State-Sponsored Terrorism." *Peace International Law Review* 14, no. 1 (2002): 77-119. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.58948/2331-3536.1189>.
- Cordovez, Diego, and Selig S. Harrison. *Out of Afghanistan: The inside Story of the Soviet Withdrawal*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1995.

- Corner, Emily, Helen Taylor, Isabelle Van Der Vegt, Nadine Salman, Bettina Rottweiler, Florian Hetzel, Caitlin Clemmow, Norah Schulten, and Paul Gill. "Reviewing the Links between Violent Extremism and Personality, Personality Disorders, and Psychopathy." *The Journal of Forensic Psychiatry & Psychology* 32, no. 3 (2021/05/04 2021): 378-407. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14789949.2021.1884736>.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14789949.2021.1884736>.
- "After Peshawar Blast, Muttaqi Says Pakistan Should Not Blame Others." *Tolo News*, Updated February 1 2023, 2023, <https://tolonews.com/afghanistan-181858>.
- Devasher, T. *The Pashtuns: A Contested History*. HarperCollins, 2022.
- Devji, Faisal. *Muslim Zion*. Harvard University Press, 2013.
- Fair, Carol Christine. "Militant Recruitment in Pakistan: A New Look at the Militancy–Madrasah Connection." In *Pakistan's Political Labyrinths*, 59-85: Routledge India, 2015.
- Fair, Carol Christine, Rebecca Littman, Neil Malhotra, and Jacob N. Shapiro. "Relative Poverty, Perceived Violence, and Support for Militant Politics: Evidence from Pakistan." *Political Science Research and Methods* 6, no. 1 (2018): 57-81. <https://doi.org/10.1017/psrm.2016.6>.
<https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/3AEAF20C324355E612F10AF59BC1DC38>.
- Gabol, Imran. "Mob Storms Police Station, Lynches 'Blasphemy' Accused." *Dawn (Karachi)*, February 12, 2023 2023. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1736708/mob-storms-police-station-lynches-blasphemy-accused>.
- Gill, Paul, John Horgan, and Paige Deckert. "Bombing Alone: Tracing the Motivations and Antecedent Behaviors of Lone-Actor Terrorists." *Journal of Forensic Sciences* 59, no. 2 (2014): 425-35. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/1556-4029.12312>.
- Graff, Corinne. "Poverty, Development, and Violent Extremism in Weak States." In *Confronting Poverty : Weak States and U.S. National Security*, edited by Susan E. Rice, Corinne Graff and Carlos Pascual. Washington, DC: The Brookings Institution, 2010.
- Gunaratna, Rohan, and Khuram Iqbal. *Pakistan : Terrorism Ground Zero*. London: Reaktion Books Ltd, 2011.
- . *Pakistan: Terrorism Ground Zero*. 2011.
- Hafez, Mohammed, and Creighton Mullins. "The Radicalization Puzzle: A Theoretical Synthesis of Empirical Approaches to Homegrown Extremism." *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 38, no. 11 (2015/11/02 2015): 958-75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610X.2015.1051375>.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610X.2015.1051375>.
- Hanif, Muhammad. "Pakistan, Land of the Intolerant." *The New York Times*, November 19 2017. <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/10/19/opinion/pakistan-muslims-ahmadis.html>.
- Hansen, David. *The Threat of Growing Extremism in Punjab*. Norwegian Peacebuilding Resource Centre (2012).
<https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/156609/0b5ea152f1a7a2e9f40be540e08a4484.pdf>.
- Haqqani, Husain. *Pakistan: Between Mosque and Military*. Lahore: Vanguard Books, 2005.
- . *Reimagining Pakistan: Transforming a Dysfunctional Nuclear State*. HarperCollins India, 2020.

- Haque, Raheem ul. "Can Pakistan Have a De- Radicalised Future?". Chap. 4 In Rethinking Pakistan, edited by Bilal Zahoor and Raza Rumi. A 21st Century Perspective, 51-58: Anthem Press, 2020.
- . Youth Radicalization in Pakistan. United States Institute of Peace (February 26, 2014 2014).
https://www.usip.org/sites/default/files/PB%20167_Youth_Radicalization_in_Pakistan.pdf
- Harris-Hogan, Shandon, Kate Barrelle, and Andrew Zammit. "What Is Countering Violent Extremism? Exploring Cve Policy and Practice in Australia." Behavioral Sciences of Terrorism and Political Aggression 8, no. 1 (2016): 6-24.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/19434472.2015.1104710>.
- Hashmi, Arshi Saleem. "Historical Roots of the Deobandi Version of Jihadism and Its Implications for Violence in Today's Pakistan." Chap. 5 In Faith-Based Violence and Deobandi Militancy in Pakistan, edited by Jawad Syed, Edwina Pio, Tahir Kamran and Abbas Zaidi: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016.
- Hayes, Sherrill W. "Changing Radicalization to Resilience by Understanding Marginalization." Peace Review: A Journal of Social Justice 29 (2017): 153–59.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/10402659.2017.1308190>.
- HRCIP. State of Human Rights in 2022. Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (2023).
<https://hrcp-web.org/hrcpweb/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/2023-State-of-human-rights-in-2022.pdf>.
- Husain, Mujahid. Punjabi Taliban: Driving Extremism in Pakistan. Pentagon Press, 2012.
- Hussain, Kashif. "From Pulpit to Marketplace: The Evolution of Religious Political Parties in Pakistan." World Affairs 187, no. 2 (2024): 151-60. <https://doi.org/10.1002/waf2.12021>.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/waf2.12021>.
- Iannaccone, Laurence R, and Eli Berman. "Religious Extremism: The Good, the Bad, and the Deadly." Public choice 128 (2006): 109-29.
- Ispahani, Farahnaz. Purifying the Land of the Pure Pakistan's Religious Minorities. Noida, Uttar Pradesh: Harper Collins, 2018.
- Jahangir, Asma. "Pakistan's Tenets of the Faith." New Statesman, April 14, 2011, 2011.
- Jalal, Ayesha. Partisans of Allah: Jihad in South Asia. Harvard University Press, 2008.
- . The Struggle for Pakistan: A Muslim Homeland and Global Politics. The Belknap Press, 2014.
- Jasko, Katarzyna, Gary LaFree, James Piazza, and Michael H. Becker. "A Comparison of Political Violence by Left-Wing, Right-Wing, and Islamist Extremists in the United States and the World." Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences 119, no. 30 (2022): e2122593119.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.1073/pnas.2122593119>.
<https://www.pnas.org/doi/abs/10.1073/pnas.2122593119>.
- Javaid, Umbreen. "Partnership in War on Terror and Mounting Militant Extremism in Pakistan." South Asian Studies 26, no. 2 (2011): 227-39.
https://pu.edu.pk/images/journal/csas/PDF/V_26_No_2_1Dr.%20Umbreen%20Javaid.pdf

- Justino, Patricia. Revisiting the Links between Economic Inequality and Political Violence: The Role of Social Mobilization. WIDER Working Paper, 2022.
- Kamran, Tahir. "Majlis-I-Ahrar-I-Islam: Religion, Socialism and Agitation in Action." *South Asian History and Culture* 4, no. 4 (2013/10/01 2013): 465-82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19472498.2013.824678>.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/19472498.2013.824678>.
- . "The Pre-History of Religious Exclusionism in Contemporary Pakistan: Khatam-E-Nubuwwat 1889–1953." *Modern Asian Studies* 49 (03/11 2015): 1-35. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0026749X14000043>.
- Kennedy, Robert Francis. "Extremism, Left and Right." Chap. 7 In *The Pursuit of Justice*, edited by Robert Francis Kennedy and Theodore J. Lowi: Harper & Row, 1964.
- Khan, Akbar. "Steps-to-War Theory and Interstate Wars in the Middle East: Is State-Sponsored Terrorism Another Escalating Step?". *Journal of Asian and African Studies* 56, no. 7 (2021): 1521-37.
- Khan, Akbar, and Han Zhaoying. "Conflict Escalation in the Middle East Revisited: Thinking through Interstate Rivalries and State-Sponsored Terrorism." *Israel Affairs* 26, no. 2 (2020): 242-56.
- Khan, Hamid. *Constitutional and Political History of Pakistan*. 3 ed. Karachi: OUP, 2017.
- "Pakistan's Hafiz Saeed: Is 'Charity Leader' Linked to Kashmir Attacks?" *British Broadcasting Corporation News*, 2017, accessed 10 October, 2023, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-38596301>.
- Khan, Sher Ali, Shakeel Ahmed, and Fareedullah Chaudhry. "Punjab's 'Encounters' with Sectarianism." *Herald*, 2016. <https://herald.dawn.com/news/print/1153564>.
- Khosa, Tariq. "The Miasma of Hate." *Opinion, Dawn (Islamabad)*, December 5 2015. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1224243>.
- "Azam-E-Istehkam Not a 'Large-Scale Military Operation,' Clarifies Pm Sharif Amid Growing Criticism." *Arab News Pakistan*, 2024, accessed July 15, 2024, <https://www.arabnews.pk/node/2537021/pakistan>.
- Koomen, W., and J. V. D. Pligt. *The Psychology of Radicalization and Terrorism*. Routledge, 2016.
- Krieger, T., and D. Meierrieks. "Income Inequality, Redistribution and Domestic Terrorism." *World Development* 116 (2019): 125-36. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.12.008>.
- Krueger, Alan B., and Jitka Malec̣kova. "Education, Poverty and Terrorism: Is There a Causal Connection?". *Journal of Economic Perspectives* 17, no. 4 (2003): 119–44. <https://www.sas.rochester.edu/psc/clarke/214/Krueger03.pdf>.
- Kruglanski, Arie W., Michele J. Gelfand, Jocelyn J. Bélanger, Anna Sheveland, Malkanthi Hetiarachchi, and Rohan Gunaratna. "The Psychology of Radicalization and Deradicalization: How Significance Quest Impacts Violent Extremism." *Political Psychology* 35, no. S1 (2014): 69-93. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12163>.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/pops.12163>.
- Kundnani, Arun, and Ben Hayes. *The Globalisation of Countering Violent Extremism Policies Undermining Human Rights, Instrumentalising Civil Society*. Transnational Institute

- (Amsterdam: 2018). https://www.preventwatch.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/014092_26ca35cecec34464a5419fb6e72bf7e9.pdf.
- Lafoz Ortín, Lydia, Claudia Pérez Forniés, and Marcos Sanso-Navarro. "Horizontal Inequality and Conflict: An Empirical Assessment." SSRN (2022): 4165083.
- Lahai, John Idriss, Karin Von Stokirch, Howard Brasted, and Helen Ware, eds. *Governance and Political Adaptation in Fragile States*: Palgrave Macmillan, 2019.
- . "Introduction." In *Governance and Political Adaptation in Fragile States*, edited by John Idriss Lahai, Karin Von Stokirch, Howard Brasted and Helen Ware, 1-11: Palgrave Macmillan, 2019.
- Mirahmadi, Hedieh, Waleed Ziad, Mehreen Farooq, and Robert Lamb. *Empowering Pakistan's Civil Society to Counter Global Violent Extremism*. The Brookings (The Brookings, 2015). <https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/Empowering-Pakistans-Civil-Society-to-Counter-Violent-Extremism-English.pdf>.
- Moghaddam, F. M. "The Staircase to Terrorism: A Psychological Exploration." [In eng]. *Am Psychol* 60, no. 2 (Feb-Mar 2005): 161-9. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066x.60.2.161>.
- Mumtaz, A. . *Continuity and Change in the Traditional System of Islamic Education: The Case of Pakistan*. Karachi: Oxford University Press, 2000.
- Pakistan, Government of. *The Constituent Assembly of Pakistan Debates*. Karachi, 1949.
- Paracha, Nadeem Farooq. "The Conflicted Self: The Existential Battle between Being Muslim and Islamic in Pakistan." In *Rethinking Pakistan*, edited by Bilal Zahoor and Raza Rumi. *A 21st Century Perspective*, 41-50: Anthem Press, 2020.
- Pilger, John. *The New Rulers of the World*. Verso Books, 2016.
- Punjab, Government of. *Report of the Court of Inquiry Constituted under Punjab Act Ii of 1954 to Enquire into the Punjab Disturbances of 1953*. Lahore: Government of Punjab, 1954.
- Qazi, Shehzad H. "Rebels of the Frontier: Origins, Organization, and Recruitment of the Pakistani Taliban." *Small Wars & Insurgencies* 22, no. 4 (2011): 574-602.
- Quraish, Muhammad, and Islam Fakhir ul. "Peace-Making Efforts in Kp: An Analysis of Mma, Anp and Pti Governments (2002-18)." *Policy Perspectives* 15, no. 3 (2018): 197-208. <https://doi.org/10.13169/polipers.15.3.0197>. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.13169/polipers.15.3.0197>.
- Quraish, Muhammad, and Fakhirul Islam. "Peace-Making Efforts in Kp: An Analysis of Mma, Anp and Pti Governments (2002-18)." *Policy Perspectives: The Journal of the Institute of Policy Studies* 15, no. 3 (2018): 197-208. <https://doi.org/10.13169/polipers.15.3.0197>.
- Rahman, Fatima Z. "Pakistan: A Conducive Setting for Islamist Violence against Ahmadis." In *Faith-Based Violence and Deobandi Militancy in Pakistan*, edited by Jawad Syed, Edwina Pio, Tahir Kamran and Abbas Zaidi, 209-30. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2016.
- Rahman, T. *Denizens of Alien Worlds: A Study of Education, Inequality and Polarization in Pakistan*. Karachi: Oxford University Press, 2004.
- Rana, Amir, and Safdar Sial. *Pakistan's Evolving Militant Landscape: State Responses and Policy Options*. Pak Institute for Peace Studies (PIPS) (Islamabad: 2024). https://www.pakpips.com/web/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Final-Report_RNE_withthitlesandmaps-.pdf.

- Rana, Muhammad Amir. "Threat of Religious Extremism." Chap. 12 In *Pakistan: The Search for Stability*, edited by Maleeha Lodhi: Hurst Publishers, 2024.
- Rashid, Ahmed. *Descent into Chaos: The United States and the Failure of Nation Building in Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Central Asia*. First Edition ed.: Viking, 2008.
- . *Descent into Chaos: The Us and the Disaster in Pakistan, Afghanistan and Central Asia*. New York: Penguin Books, 2008.
- . *Pakistan on the Brink: The Future of America, Pakistan, and Afghanistan*. First Edition ed.: Viking, 2012.
- Rice, Susan E. "Poverty and State Weakness." In *Confronting Poverty : Weak States and U.S. National Security*, edited by Susan E. Rice, Corinne Graff and Carlos Pascual. Washington, DC: The Brookings Institution, 2010.
- Sadiq, Imran. "Sialkot Mob Lynches Sri Lankan Factory Manager, Burns Corpse over Blasphemy Allegations." *Dawn* (Islamabad), December 3, 2021. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1661728>.
- Sambanis, Nicholas. "Poverty and the Organization of Political Violence: A Review and Some Conjectures." *Brookings Trade Forum* 2004, Washington, DC, Brookings Institution, 2005.
- Schwartz, Seth J., Curtis S. Dunkel, and Alan S. Waterman. "Terrorism: An Identity Theory Perspective." *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 32, no. 6 (2009): 537-59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10576100902888453>.
- Siddiqi, Farhan. *The Politics of Ethnicity in Pakistan: The Baloch, Sindhi and Mohajir Ethnic Movements*. Oxford: Routledge, 2012. doi:10.4324/9780203123089.
- Silke, Andrew. "Holy Warriors: Exploring the Psychological Processes of Jihadi Radicalization." *European Journal of Criminology* 5 (2008): 99-123. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477370807084226>.
- Smith, W.C. *Islam in Modern History*. Princeton University Press, 1957.
- Susan E. Rice, Corinne Graff, and Janet Lewis. *Poverty and Civil War: What Policymakers Need to Know*. Brookings (2006).
- Syed, Jawad, Edwina Pio, Tahir Kamran, and Abbas Zaidi, eds. *Faith-Based Violence and Deobandi Militancy in Pakistan*: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016.
- Taji-Farouki, S., and B. M. Nafi. *Islamic Thought in the Twentieth Century*. I. B. Tauris, 2004.
- Toor, Saadia. *The State of Islam: Culture and Cold War Politics in Pakistan*. Pluto Press, 2011. doi:10.2307/j.ctt183pb4d.
- Ullah, Haroon K. *Vying for Allah's Vote: Understanding Islamic Parties, Political Violence, and Extremism in Pakistan*. Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press, 2014.
- UNDP. *Preventing and Responding to Violent Extremism in Africa: A Development Approach*. (New York: 2015).
- . *Preventing Violent Extremism through Promoting Inclusive Development, Tolerance and Respect for Diversity*. (2016).
- Valentine, S.R. *Islam and the Ahmadiyya Jama'at: History, Belief, Practice*. Hurst & Company, 2008.
- Waseem, Muhammad. *Political Conflict in Pakistan*. Hurst, 2021.
- Wiktorowicz, Q. *Radical Islam Rising: Muslim Extremism in the West*. Rowman & Littlefield, 2005.

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Online ISSN (3006-1504)

Print ISSN (3006-1490)

- Yasmeen, Samina, and FoZIA Umar. "Religious Extremism and Sectarianism in Pakistan: An Appraisal." *Journal of the Research Society of Pakistan* 58, no. 2 (2021): 59.
- Yusoufzai, K., and F. Emmerling. "How Identity Crisis, Relative Deprivation, Personal Characteristics, and Empathy Contribute to the Engagement of Western Individuals in Islamist Terrorist Behavior." *Journal of Terrorism Research* 8, no. 1 (2017): 68-80. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.15664/jtr.1292>.
- Zahab, Mariam Abou. *Pakistan: A Kaleidoscope of Islam*. Comparative Politics and International Studies. Edited by Christophe Jaffrelot. Hurst, 2020.
- Zahid, Farhan. *The Roots of Violent Islamic Activism in South Asia*. Narratives, 2014.
- Zeb, Khan, and Zahid Shahab Ahmed. "Structural Violence and Terrorism in the Federally Administered Tribal Areas of Pakistan." *Civil Wars* 21, no. 1 (2019/01/02 2019): 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13698249.2019.1586334>.